

LEGITIMACY OF GREEN SOLOW MODEL AND ENVIRONMENTAL KUZNETS CURVE: A PANEL ANALYSIS FOR ASIAN COUNTRIES

Awais Jabbar

School Education Department, Government of Punjab, Pakistan

ABSTRACT: Legitimate countries try to sustain economic growth and on the other side face pollutant emissions during the production process. Global warming and climate changes are the results of these pollutant emissions. The study estimates the environmental Kuznets curve (EKC) hypothesis empirically in the panel of Asian developed and developing countries. The study used data for five countries ranges from 1981 to 2010. The empirical results are obtained by fixed effect method. In addition, dynamic relationship between CO₂ emission per capita, energy consumption per capita, export product diversification (Theil index) and economic growth per capita is checked. The value of Theil index suggests that in developed countries export product diversification is elastic whereas it is inelastic in developing countries. It suggests that developed countries export-basket has items with fewer pollutant emissions. On other hand, export-basket of developing countries still has large pollutant emission items. The energy consumption in industries for production contributes to CO₂ emission. The GDP per capita is positively associated with CO₂ emission whereas, squared GDP per capita has a reducing role in CO₂ emission. The signs of GDP and squared GDP per capita provide the evidence of EKC hypothesis. In addition to that, the study also checks the validity of Green Solow model in Asian developed and developing countries. The validity is checked with Mann-Kendall trend test. The results infer that except Singapore, no other country exhibits the initial increase and then decreasing trend to support the Green Solow model. Moreover, the graphical representation of Mann-Kendall trend test indicates that GDP or economic growth trend is higher than the emission trend in Hong Kong and Singapore.

KEYWORDS: Green Solow Model; Environmental Kuznets curve; Mann-Kendall Trend test; CO₂ Emissions

1. INTRODUCTION

Energy is a lifeline for any economy. Over the past 2 decades, industrialization has played an important role in the utilization of energy by burning nonrenewable resources. The expansion of industrialization helps in combating poverty. Poverty reduction ensures a well-managed living standard for a large population. International trends show that an increase in economic growth also boosts CO₂ emissions. Recent data reveals that CO₂ emissions are 150 times higher than in 1850. In 1850 CO₂ emissions were 198 MTCO₂ and which has increased to 32274 MTCO₂ in 2016. Developed and developing countries disagree on concepts of energy consumption. Disagreed concepts are the constraints on energy consumption as they hinder economic growth. Accordingly, it is recommended that industrial countries provide funds to alleviate global warming. The fund allocations measure industrial efforts to reduce emission levels. Countries try to stabilize energy consumption on one side and sustainable economic growth on the other side. Energy consumption increases global warming and climate changes, which puts pressure on countries towards combating these problems.

Negative externalities caused by industrialization bring about a decline in the domestic product due to Green House Gases (GHG) emission on a large scale. Pakistan is an agrarian economy that provides raw material to the industrial sector. Pakistan is the 42nd largest economy in the world by subject to GDP. Oil, gas, coal are the major components of energy consumption. The industrial oil consumption pattern of Pakistan shows a tremendous increase from previous years. Total industrial oil consumption was 937,355 (Tons) in 2014-15, which increased to 1,088,255 (Tons) in 2015-16 (Economic Survey of Pakistan 2015-16). Energy, economy and environment are closely related to each other. Industry is the energy-consuming sector that contributes major emission to GHG. For this reason, Pakistan is an important country for including in this study which is responsible for contributing its share in world

Corresponding Author Email: awaisjabbar22@yahoo.com

pollutant emissions. Expansion of industries creates a harmful effect on the quality of the environment. The utilization of carbon-producing resources in industries causes negative externalities in form of CO₂ and other harmful emissions. So, it is necessary to test empirically the industrial emission and its negative externalities.

The economist basically tests the long-run and short-run relation between CO₂ and economic development with help of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (Akin, 2014; Gozgor & Can, 2016; Shahbaz, Hye, Tiwari, & Leitão, 2013). (Grossman & Krueger, 1995) first introduced an empirical testification of Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis. It was believed that for sustainable economic growth, environmental degradation should get worse. The EKC hypothesis explains that at the initial stage economic growth increases due to industrialization, and environmental degradation occurs. Initially, environmental pollution increase with the increase in economic growth. But after a certain point, environmental degradation starts to reduce. So, EKC shows an inverted U-shaped relationship. At first stage, countries try their best to achieve economic growth by industrialization at the cost of environmental degradation. Here "Environmental Quality" becomes secondary importance but when high-income level is attained, environmental quality becomes the top priority. In other words, policymakers try to implement environmentally friendly policies and technologies.

Some studies find the relationship between environmental degradation, economic growth and energy consumption while controlling for other independent variables. These studies involve the variables of financial development, trade openness, tourism, population density, FDI and capital to GDP ratio (Javid & Sharif, 2016; Kanjilal & Ghosh, 2013). Most of the studies use trade openness and the volume of exports as a proxy for international trade. However, it's not only the volume of trade that matters but the diversification of export products also plays an important role in CO₂ emission. In order to expand domestic export basket, many new products are produced. In fact, for purpose of producing these products, the country tries to expand its economy and moves towards industrialization. Industrialization is important for any country as it helps to improve the economic position of the country. But industrialization creates negative externalities in form of CO₂, CH₄ and other GHG emissions. So diversification of export products is an important variable to estimate these effects which are missing in the literature regarding Asian developed and developing countries.

Developed and developing countries pollutants emission level differs on the basis of abatement efforts. Abatement efforts define as "Government actions and policies to reduce pollution level by introducing environment-friendly practices". (William A Brock & Taylor, 2010) introduced the augmented traditional Solow model. The model describes a one-sector economy where output is produced with help of capital and labor. The model depends upon the saving function and abatement function. Saving function is responsible for generating capital in the economy. Capital circulates in the economy and helps in producing output. Output produces with the development of industrialization and indirectly spawns pollution in the economy. Abatement function describes the efforts to reduce this pollution by introducing new technologies which are referred to as "Abatement cost". Abatement has positive but diminishing effects on pollution reduction. This was called the "Green Solow Model" by (William A Brock & Taylor, 2010). The Green Solow Model (GSM) is interlinked with the Environmental Kuznets Curve. Both models illustrate the same convergence at the optimal economic point as described by (Solow, 1956; Swan, 1956).

There are two reasons to study the problem of industrialization and its externalities in the case of developed and developing countries. Firstly, in developing countries, industrial activities and other biological emissions of greenhouse gases reduce GDP at a large scale. Urbanization causes industrial

expansion which leads to an increase in CO₂ and other harmful emissions. Furthermore, the mixing of industrial chemical waste with freshwater affects the cattle's life, reduce the production of crops, decrease yielding capacities of land. The burning of non-renewable resources like coal, oil and gas for the production of energy leads to CO₂ emissions and negatively affects the quality of the environment. In this sense, every year GDP of developing countries shrinks at a large scale (Antoci, Russu, Sordi, & Ticci, 2014).

Secondly, according to Climate Resource Institute, the developed economies are major emitters. Their efforts to focus on the abatement of emissions in the form of abatement cost will make them clean economies. On the other side, developing countries have fewer emissions due to small scale expansion of industrialization. But their efforts towards the abatement of emissions lag as compared to developed economies. The abatement efforts by developed and developing countries are considered with the help of Green Solow Model.

This study explains the relationship between industrialization and Green House Gas Emissions (Environmental externalities). The focus of the study is on Asian developed and developing countries. In the first step, the study estimates the relationship between CO₂ emissions, economic growth of the economy, energy consumption, and industrial growth by controlling the effect of export product diversification. Secondly, the study checks the validity of Green Solow Model for CO₂ emissions in the mention region. To the best of my knowledge, no study has incorporated EKC and GSM simultaneously in case of Asian developed and developing countries.

The rest of the paper proceeds as follows: Literature review is discussed in Section 2. Section 3 provides the methodology of research with details explanation of empirical model and econometric technique. Section 4 describes the results and discussion. Section 5 presents the conclusion and policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

(Shahbaz et al., 2013) studied the relationship between environmental Kuznets curve and energy consumption in case of Romania. The study involves three variables GDP, energy consumption and CO₂ emission. The study involves time period of 1980-2010 by using of ARDL technique. The results show short run and long run effect of Environmental Kuznets curve Romania. Moreover, results show that democratic regimes put positive effect in establishing of policies that are effective in reducing environmental techniques.

(Ali, Khatoon, Ather, & Akhtar, 2015) examines the relationship between energy consumption, carbon emission and economic growth in case of Pakistan. The time period ranges from 1980-2012. In order to capture the causality and relation among variables econometric techniques are use. The Johansen co-integration approach employed to check long run relation among said variables. The co-integration technique reveals the long run effective relationship among variables but not in short runs. Unidirectional causality runs from energy consumption to carbon emissions.

(Saboori & Sulaiman, 2013) explored the relationship between economic growth and carbon emissions in case of Malaysia. The long run effect is capture by using ARDL approach by using data period from 1980 to 2009. The empirical findings suggest the long run relationship exist between per capita carbon emission and per capita economic growth of Malaysia. The granger causality that involve VECM shows deficiency to consider short run effect between variables, but unidirectional causality runs from economic growth to carbon emissions in long

run.

(W A Brock & Taylor, 2004) demonstrates empirical findings between Environmental Kuznets curve and key macrocosmic model that is Solow model. The Solow model is amended by technological progress in abatement. The amended model is called as “Green Solow Model” that Shows Environmental Kuznets curve relationship between flow of pollution emission and income per capita as well as environmental stock quality and per capita income. The theoretical framework of model shows the results that amended Solow model and EKC both are interrelate to each other.

(Antoci et al., 2014) established a study that examined the role played by environmental negative externalities and their effect on two sectors economy. Moreover, this study examines the externalities effect on shaping inter-sectoral mobility of labor and economic heterogeneous agents. The results show that due to industrialization, equilibrium properties of economy effect and that leads to reduce economic welfare by increasing in emissions. Furthermore, it is also be noted that industrialization is associated with workers welfare in agriculture sector.

(Gozgor & Can, 2016) employed the relationship between export product diversification and Environmental Kuznets curve in case of Turkey for period of 1971 to 2010. The study use time series data. To check long run and short run effect unit root with structural breaks and co-integration analysis for multiple endogenous breaks are employed. The results show the EKC hypothesis is valid both in short and long run in Turkey. Moreover, increase in export products diversifies basket cause CO₂ emission increase at tremendous rate.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The study explains the Green Solow Model and Environmental Kuznets Curve in case of Asian developed and developing countries. The effect of export product diversification on carbon dioxide emission will also be checked in case of developed and developing countries of Asia region. The data covers the range from 1981 to 2010. The study takes Hong Kong, China, Thailand, Singapore and Japan as Asian developed countries. The developing countries are India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Iran and Malaysia. The variable of energy consumption (kilogram of oil equivalent) per capita, real GDP per capita and squared real GDP per capita (constant \$ price in 2005) is used as independent variable obtained from dataset of world development indicators (WDI). The energy effect is captured with help of energy consumption variable. Utilization of energy from non-renewable resources results in tremendous increase of carbon dioxide emission.

The extensive expansion of industrialization put pressure on utilization of energy provided sources like coal, oil etc. Consequently, emissions in the economy increase. So energy consumption is main component of emissions formation. The economic growth effect is captured by the variables of real GDP per capita and squared real GDP per capita. The economies efforts towards increase in income level of person highlights the importance of industrialization as final goods yields more income than primary goods. For the sake of industrialization better management and policies are to be design. The focus of these policies is just on the improvement of living standard, but they neglect the resulting externalities creates in the form of environmental degradation. The industries are planted and GDP of country improve. The increase in income level is on behalf of extensive pollutants emission. The trade variable export product diversification will also be considered as explanatory variable obtained from international monetary fund. The dataset of export product diversification is recently compiled by International Monetary Fund (IMF) which includes indexes of market to destination. The main focus of

dataset is on indexes of exporting commodities partners and diversification across products. The Theil index will be used for export product diversification index. All the explanatory variables will be taken in the form of logarithmic. Moreover, more the value of Theil index represents less product diversification.

The including of export product diversification variable is important in the context of developing countries due to narrow export basket. The narrow export basket shows the country current export products. When developing countries put a step forward to improve per capita income, the main focus among trade components is on expansion of export product basket. The export basket diversification is improved by putting more industries that leads to negative environmental externalities. These externalities cover positive and negative aspects. Expansion of industries is important for economy as it helps in providing employment opportunities to unemployed people. The introducing of new technologies in production personified skills in labor. Consequently, increase output lift up the economy and income level of economy raise from previous level. This is positive aspect of product diversification.

Secondly, Social benefit is achieved at the cost of social interest. When expansion of industries takes place, major focus is on energy availability. Utilization of non-renewable resources creates negative externalities in the form of emission pollutants. In this way, economy increases its income level but it also faces severe environmental degradation.

The developed economies have wide range of export products. The developed countries focus is on sustainable growth of export products, not on the expansion due to which emission level is low. These countries already faced environmental degradation in past, when moved from developing to developed state. On other hand, narrow export basket put pressure on developing countries for industrialization. Consequently, emission level is high in these countries. The focus of study will differentiate emissions level of developed and developing countries of Asian region empirically.

The carbon dioxide emission (metric tons per capita) is used as dependent variable in panel of Asian developed and developing countries. The variable of carbon dioxide emission is important in the sense that all the activities of industrialization results to increase of pollutants. Among these pollutants carbon dioxide is major pollutant that adversely effected the environment. The dataset of dependent variable will obtained from WDI.

3.1 Empirical Methodology

The carbon dioxide emissions determinants are captured by consider the following model.

$$\text{LNCO}_2 = f(\text{RGDP}, \text{RGDP}^2, \text{ENC}, \text{INDGR}, \text{EXPDIV})$$

The panel regression model is

$$\text{LNCO}_{2i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{GDP}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{GDP}^2_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{ENC}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{EXPDIV}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_i$$

Where t refers the time period, $\text{GDP}_{i,t}$ is the real GDP per capita, $\text{GDP}^2_{i,t}$ is the squared GDP per capita, $\text{ENC}_{i,t}$ is the energy consumption, $\text{INDGR}_{i,t}$ is the industrial growth, $\text{EXPDIV}_{i,t}$ is the export product diversification. Where LN is natural log.

The expected sign of parameters are: $\beta_0 > 0$, $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 < 0$, $\beta_3 > 0$. The environmental Kuznets curve is found to exist, if GDP has positive value and Squared GDP has negative value. If this is not found than there is no existence of environmental Kuznets curve in economy. The expected value of export product diversification parameter is positive or negative depend upon the economic development stage of economy. If the economy is still survive in developing concept, it describes the country is producing emission producing products. In this case, the $\beta_4 < 0$ (the value is in negative).

The data use the panel data approach with fixed and random effect for measurement of parameters. Moreover, the study use the Mann-Kandall tau trend test to check the validity of green Solow model and EKC trend in Asian developed and developing countries.

3.2 Green Solow Model

(William A Brock & Taylor, 2010) present an extension of traditional Solow model, which they called as Green Solow Model. The model exogenously set the saving rates and abatement choices. The economy produced output by employing the units of labor and capital at constant return to scale.

The production function is

$$Y_t = F(K_t, B_t L_t)$$

Where B_t = productivity of labor. Capital for output is generates with saving rates "s" and capital depreciates at fixed rate δ . The pollution generated directly by output. If the pollution remains unabated, each unit of output generates Ω_t units of pollution at every point in time. Hitherto, economy devote constant and exogenous fraction of output to abate the pollution on economy. The unit of pollution a (θ) Ω_t is generated from each unit of output. Where a (θ) is abatement function that satisfy a $(0) = 1$, a' $(\theta) < 0$ and a'' $(\theta) > 0$. The abatement has positive but diminishing marginal impact on pollution reduction. L_t is labor force grow at constant rate of n. B_t is labor productivity grow at constant and exogenous growth rate g. Exogenous technological progress in abatement lowers Ω_t at a constant rate $g_A > 0$. Thus, the model is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_t &= (1-\theta)F(K_t, B_t L_t) & K_t &= sY_t - \delta K_t & P_t &= a(\theta)\Omega_t F(K_t, B_t L_t) \\ L_t &= nL_t & B_t &= gB_t & \Omega_t &= -g_A \Omega_t \end{aligned}$$

(William A Brock & Taylor, 2010) basically introduce the structural model which is named as Green solow model. This model explains the CO₂ emission, its working mechanism and describes the solow type convergence of CO₂ emission growth from the initial emissions. The model assumes CO₂ emission intensity growth (CEIG) as constant. (Stefanski, 2010) argue that the role of CEIG as constant is limited. The EKC trajectory is only attainable with large set of data. The Mann-kendall trend test is conducted to check the validity of green solow model and existing of EKC trajectory.

3.3 Mann-Kendall Trend Test

The validity of green Solow model in set of Asian developed and developing countries is obtain by apply of Mann-kendall trend test. The paper follow the (Chen, 2017) work for apply the trend test who check the green Solow model validity by considering EKC trajectory for 21 Eurpeon countries. The increasing and decreasing trends for each series are tested. The Mann-kendall trend test has been used many times for analayzing the environmental effects due to climate change.

The working principle of trend is; to check any increase and decrease trend of series, a trend indicator S is defined as

$$S = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sum_{i=j+1}^n \text{sign}(x_j - x_i)$$

$$\Theta = x_j - x_i, \text{ and } \text{sign}(\Theta) = +1 \text{ if } \Theta > 0, \quad 0 \text{ if } \Theta = 0, \quad -1 \text{ if } \Theta < 0$$

Moreover, the above estimation provides us with Kendall's Tau correlation test. The trend significance for the series can be tested by assuming that S is normally distributed. Thus, a hypothesis can be made to confirm the increasing and decreasing trend of series for a specific period of time. The null hypothesis against its alternative hypothesis can be made as follow:

H₀: no trend exists

H₁: a trend exists.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 and 2, explains the fixed and random effect results of developing and developed countries of Asia. By rejecting the null hypothesis, results show robustness under fixed effect model. In table 1, dependent variable is CO₂ as CO₂ emission per capita. The positive and negative signs of coefficients show the impact of independent variable on dependent variable. The coefficient of GDP as real GDP per capita is 0.001446 and it has statistically significant effect on CO₂ emission per capita with t-value of 10.89 and probability of 0.0000. The Real GDP per capita coefficient is significant at level of 5%. The coefficient value suggests that increase in real GDP does add to CO₂ emission. Thus the result explains that 1% increase in real GDP per capita will lead to increase the per capita CO₂ emission by 0.001446% in selected Asian developing countries. In table 2, for case of selected Asian developed countries CO₂ emission per capita is Dependent variable. The coefficient value of real GDP per capita suggests that 1% increase in real GDP cause the CO₂ emission per capita increase by 0.0000983%. The real GDP coefficient is statistically significant with t-value 2.87 and probability of 0.0048. The real GDP coefficient findings are consistent with (Kaika & Zervas, 2013; Kanjilal & Ghosh, 2013).

In table 1, the coefficient of squared real GDP per capita is -0.000000144. It has negative and statistically insignificant effect on CO₂ emission per capita with t-value of -10.7 and probability of 0.0000. The coefficient of squared real GDP has significant effect on CO₂ emission. The coefficient value suggests that 1% increase in Squared Real GDP per capita will lead to decrease CO₂ emission per capita by 0.000000144% in developing countries. In table 2, for developed countries squared real GDP per capita coefficient value is -0.0000000253 that is statistically significant. The 1% increase in squared real GDP per capita results in decrease of CO₂ emission per capita by 0.0000000253%.

In Table 1, study finds that energy consumption has positive and statistically significant effect at 5% level on CO₂ emission per capita. It suggests that 1% increase in energy consumption will lead the CO₂ emission increase by 0.000257% in developing countries. The t value (2.68) and probability (0.0083) supports the significance of energy consumption coefficient. Table 2, suggests that energy consumption has positive effect on CO₂ emission. The results are significant with t-value (2.85) and probability (0.0050) at 5% level. It is suggested that 1% increase in energy consumption per capita cause to increase CO₂ emission per capita by 0.000170% in developed countries. The results here are conformable with the studies on this subject by (Halicioglu, 2009; Kanjilal & Ghosh, 2013; Muhammad, Lean, & Muhammad, 2011; Saidi & Hammami, 2015).

In table 1, the coefficient of export product diversification (Theil index) has positive effect on CO₂ emission. Moreover, the value of Theil index (0.301930) is inelastic that means export product diversification cause higher CO₂ emission in developing countries. The results indicate that 1% increase in Theil index increase CO₂ emission by 0.30%. The table 2 suggests that Theil index for developed countries is negative. The value of Theil index (-0.991076) is more elastic that means export product diversification cause less CO₂ emission in developed countries. The results suggest that 1% increase in Theil index decrease the CO₂ emission per capita by 0.99%. The results are consistent with the findings of (Aditya & Acharyya, 2013; Gozgor & Can, 2016; Kaika & Zervas, 2013; Lederman & Klinger, 2006).

The linear and nonlinear terms of real GDP that is squared real GDP per capita in Table 1 and Table 2 confirm the existence of inverted U relationship between economic growth and CO₂ emission. The negative sign of squared term seems to affirm the delinking of CO₂ emission per capita and real GDP per capita at high level of income in country. The existence of U shaped inverted EKC and its significance is statistically confirmed in Asian developed and developing countries.

4.1 Mann-Kendall Trend Test Findings and Discussion

This section examines the changes in CO₂ emission per capita in five developing and developed countries of Asia region as shown in Table 3 and evaluates EKC emission patterns by using Mann-Kendall trend test.

The data ranges from 1981 to 2010 and entire study period is divided into three sub periods, 1981-1990, 1991-2000, 2001-2010. The trends in the entire study period and three sub periods are testing by the use of Mann-Kendall trend test. Table 3 presents the Kendall Tau statistics and the significance of the trends for mentioned time periods. The green Solow model validity is achieved if the Tau statistics for whole set of periods shows initially increasing and then decreasing trends. By focusing on the Tau estimations mention in table 3, it is detectible that in case of developing countries the EKC trend is increasing. The emission trend of Iran is initially increased. No change in trend exists for period 1981-2000. After that for period of 2000-2010, the trend is again increasing.

The Tau statistics of developed countries are dissimilar from developing. The increasing trend of CO₂ emission exists in developed countries for time period of 1981-1990. The Tau value in case of Hong Kong is initially increasing and after that no change exists. Similarly, for japan trend is initially increasing for consecutive two time periods and after that no change. The trend of China and Thailand is continuously increasing. The country Singapore only reflects the validity of green Solow model where the initially trend is increasing and then decreasing.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Recently, many studies focus on empirical study of environment. Countries are paying special attention on agreements related the environment degradation due to severe effect of global warming.. The main focus of the study is on growth-environment nexus. The study checks the existence of Environmental Kuznets curve hypothesis empirically by utilize the dataset of Asian developed and developing countries. To do so, study use fixed effect model results to support the existence of EKC. The number of cross sections includes in study is Five for each developing and developed countries. The time period ranges from 1981 to 2010. The empirical findings are in line with the literature. The existence of EKC hypothesis is evidently observe from the values of economic growth per capita and square of economic growth per capita in both developed and developing countries. The energy consumption positively involve in CO₂ emission whereas export product diversification is negatively associated to CO₂ emission in developed countries and positively related to CO₂ emission in developing countries. In addition, the study investigates the dynamic relationship between CO₂ emission per capita, energy consumption per capita, export product diversification (Theil index) and GDP growth per capita, where the export oriented growth strategy has been adopted.

Moreover, the study checks the validity of green Solow model by taking the Mann-kendall trend test. The results supports that except Singapore, no other country have evidence of green Solow model.

The empirical results suggest that there should be systematic policy implications for effective reduction in CO₂ emission. Firstly, it is evidently supported by number of studies that economic growth is achieved by emission of pollutants. Economic growth is necessary for developing countries not only to come in competition with developed countries but also to generate employment opportunities for young generation. Here, the best policy is initially reducing the cost of environment friendly investment.

Secondly, many Asian countries are utilizing large part of energy consumption for production purposes and it is not feasible to reduce energy consumption. Here, it is necessary to implement effective utilization of renewable resources policy. It should be noted that tax incentives, technological subsidies

and governmental assistance are major tools for utilize renewable resources. Thirdly, nuclear energy is one of main component that helps to reduce CO₂ emission. It helps to reduce the consumption of fossils fuel. So, government should manage the large scale projects of nuclear energy production generation. Lastly, export product diversification is also major instrument for reduction of pollutant emissions. It helps to boost up the economic growth and reduce the environmental degradation. During production process, selection of those items in export basket is necessary who suppress the pollutants emission. The products having less pollutant emission should include in export basket and eliminate the products having high intensity of C₀₂ emission.

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